

Linguistic Individuality in Lexicogrammatical Alternations

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Individuality: Cognitive Linguistics

- ▶ Cognitive Linguistic/Usage-based/Emergentist (e.g. Langacker 1987, Bybee 2010)
 - ▶ Language is acquired using domain-general cognitive skills
 - ▶ Categorisation, analogy, chunking etc.
 - ▶ No innate language-specific faculty
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Individuality baked in

Individuality: Authorship Analysis

- ▶ Testing Cognitive Linguistics
 - ▶ Individuality should be measurable
 - ▶ Test implications of approach
- ▶ Applying to Forensic Linguistics
 - ▶ Individuality facilitates forensic authorship analysis
 - ▶ Scope, reliability, where to look

Individuality: Research Context

- ▶ The individual and the aggregate
 - ▶ Barlow (2013) – individual patterns of usage of functional n-grams by White House press secretaries
 - ▶ Dunn and Nini (2021) – differences between computational grammars trained on individual corpora and those trained on multi-speaker corpora
 - ▶ Anthonissen (2021) – how individual variation interacts with community-level language change in two types of passive constructions in English

Present Study

Grammatical Alternations:

Particle verb alternation (Luo 2019)

The award-winning filmmaker once said that the best advice he had ever received was simply to **pick up the pen/pick the pen up** and write.

instead of/rather than (Grieve 2016)

The villagers reverted to hunting, **instead of/rather than** trying to produce the required food solely from farming and agriculture.

Present Study

- ▶ Alternations provide potential for individual variation
- ▶ Consistent individuality may reflect uniqueness of grammar
- ▶ Research Question: Do speakers display measurable individuality in their preferences for certain variants of grammatical alternations?

Present Study: Method

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The award-winning filmmaker once said that the best advice he had ever received was simply to _____ and write.

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pick up the pen

pick the pen up

Present Study: Method

40 sentences created

Word Order (WO) Alternations (22)	Word Change (WC) Alternations (18)	
Particle Verb alternation (6)	Relative pronouns (3)	<i>instead of/rather than</i> (1)
Dative alternation (6)	<i>help/help to</i> (2)	<i>more than/over</i> (1)
Genitive alternation (6)	<i>try and/try to</i> (2)	<i>half/half of</i> (1)
<i>spray</i> alternation (2)	<i>with no/without any</i> (2)	<i>outside/outside of</i> (1)
Proper-name alternation (2)	<i>un-/not</i> (2)	<i>except/except for</i> (1)
	<i>toward/towards</i> (1)	<i>compare to/compare with</i> (1)

Present Study: Method

Participants

- ▶ n = 86, recruited via Prolific, as similar demographics as practically possible

Category	Feature
First language	English
Nationality	United Kingdom
UK area of birth	London, SE England, SW England
Highest Education level completed	Graduate degree
Gender	Woman
Age	25-45
Ethnicity (simplified)	White

Present Study: Method

Instructions:

- ▶ “From the options below each sentence, please select one to fill the gap, by pressing the 'LEFT' or 'RIGHT' arrow on your keyboard.”
- ▶ “There is no right or wrong answer; just choose what comes more naturally to you.”

Time 2, after 4-6 weeks

- ▶ Almost identical, with minor changes to reduce memory
- ▶ “another study which will have the same instructions as the first”

Collected variant selections, RTs, Prolific ID and Feedback

Present Study: Results

Research Question: Do speakers display measurable individuality in their preferences for certain variants of grammatical alternations?

- ▶ Do speakers have consistent preferences for certain variants?
- ▶ Are these preferences different to group-level preferences?

Consistency = same response at Time 1 and Time 2 to a given item

Prediction: Participants will display consistency in their variant selections, beyond the level of consistency across the group (individuality effect)

Present Study: Results

Do speakers have consistent preferences for certain variants?

Mixed-effect logistic regression using R – lme4 package (Bates et al. 2015)

- ▶ Logistic regression – binary outcome variable (variants randomly assigned 0 and 1)
- ▶ Mixed-effects – control for random effects of participant and item

```
glmer(resp_T2 ~ resp_T1 + (1 + resp_T1 | participant) + (1 + resp_T1 | item), data = results, family = 'binomial')
```

Can infer probabilities of same speaker choosing same response twice (within-speaker consistency)

Present Study: Results

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Intercept	-0.37	0.14	-2.59	0.01**
resp_T1	0.84	0.11	7.75	<0.001***

Intercept: T1 = 0 **AND** T2 = 1
 From this, can infer: T1 = 0 **AND** T2 = 0

resp_T1: T1 = 1 **AND** T2 = 1
 From this, can infer: T1 = 1 **AND** T2 = 0

Probabilities of combinations of T1 and T2 responses

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Probabilities of combinations of T1 and T2 responses

Do speakers have consistent preferences for certain variants?

Present Study: Results

Are these preferences different to group-level preferences?

- ▶ Possible that preferences are not individual, but shared across participants

Permutation procedure

- ▶ Compare within-speaker consistency with between-speaker consistency
- ▶ Fit model to real dataset
- ▶ Randomly shuffle responses to create new dataset where T1 and T2 responses given by different participants
- ▶ Fit model to new randomly permuted dataset
- ▶ Repeat 10,000 times
- ▶ Significance test: How likely is it that real results replicated by randomly permuted datasets? Less than $p = 0.05$?

Present Study: Results

Reminder: resp_T1 coefficient is an indicator of response consistency
resp_T1 coefficient for real data: within-speaker consistency
resp_T1 coefficient for permuted datasets: between-speaker consistency

Prediction: coefficient will be higher for real data than for permuted datasets

- ▶ Full model didn't converge for permutations – removed random slopes
- ▶ Real dataset: coefficient = 0.81 (c.f. 0.84 in full model)
- ▶ 0/10,000 permuted datasets had higher or equal coefficient ($M = 0.05$, $R = -0.31-0.37$)
- ▶ p = probability permuted datasets produce equal or higher coefficient than real data
- ▶ Thus, $p = <0.0001$

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Are these preferences different to group-level preferences?

Present Study: Results

So, within-speaker consistency > between-speaker consistency.

Individuality effect?... or just memory?

Conscious memory? Feedback says no:

- ▶ 12/13 said they did not remember responses

Unconscious memory/priming?

- ▶ Hypothesis: Responses given at T1 primed participants to give the same response again at T2

Present Study: Results

RT analysis:

- ▶ The less complex the cognitive task, the less time it takes (Townsend & Ashby 1983)
- ▶ Perhaps selecting T1 response made that variant easier to access and therefore preferred at T2 and selected more quickly
- ▶ In that case, T2 responses which were consistent with T1 may have lower RT than those which were not consistent

Multiple Regression: $\log_RT \sim \text{Time} + \text{Match} + \text{Time} * \text{Match}$

Memory effect prediction: significantly lower RT when Time = T2 **AND** Match = 'same'

Present Study: Results

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	8.59	0.01	652.15	<0.001***
Time_T2	-0.12	0.02	-6.66	<0.001***
Match_same	0.02	0.02	1.47	0.14
Time_T2:Match_same	-0.01	0.02	-0.47	0.64

RTs are slightly lower in general at T2

But no significant difference between matched and unmatched

RT analysis does not provide evidence for the memory effect hypothesis – that greater within-speaker consistency is due to memory/priming

Summary

Individual grammars predicted by usage-based approaches

Better understanding of individuality in language facilitates forensic authorship analysis

Present study

- ▶ Contributes to research strand evaluating individual vs group-level language
- ▶ Provides evidence of individuality in lexicogrammatical alternations
- ▶ Results in line with usage-based predictions
- ▶ Alternations as promising area for authorship analysis

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